

**INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENT:
TYPES AND TECHNIQUES OF PREPARATION**

Azamov Abbos Azam o'gli

Master of Tashkent State University of Law

Anotation: The article discusses the main aspects of the legal technique of preparing various types of international treaties.

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To date, international treaties play a leading role in international legal regulation. The legal technique of their preparation and adoption is very specific. Unfortunately, the level of training of university graduates in this field leaves much to be desired. The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties states: "An international treaty means an international agreement concluded between States in writing and governed by international law, regardless of whether such an agreement is contained in one document, two or several related documents, as well

as regardless of its specific name". Article 2 of the said Convention contains special terminology (legal thesaurus) used in the international contractual sphere: treaty, ratification, acceptance, approval, accession, international act, powers, reservation, negotiating State, contracting State, party, third State, international organization. At the same time, Part 2 specifically stipulates that the use of terms in this Convention does not affect the use of these terms or the meanings that can be given to them in the internal law of any State. By direct reception, these terms were included in the Federal Law "On International Treaties of the Russian Federation".

International treaties, being essentially international agreements, have various forms and names: the actual treaty (agreement), convention, agreement, pact, memorandum, protocol, etc. At the same time, each type is unique and may require specific legal and technical techniques. However, all contracts have a certain set of features that must be taken into account when preparing them. The classical scheme of the contract requires a preamble, definition of its purpose and objectives, conceptual the apparatus (definitions of concepts and terms), the content part, establishing the procedure and conditions for the entry into force of the contract, determining the procedure for dispute settlement, final and transitional provisions.

The preamble of an international treaty has a special form of construction. In it, the parties, declaring their commitment to the principles of international law, determine the direction of development of international relations in the area regulated by the treaty, declare their desire to follow the accepted agreements. In some cases, in the absence of a preamble, to a certain extent, however, in a stricter form, the wording can replace its goals and objectives of the agreement.

Exceptional attention in the preparation of the international the contract has a working out of the conceptual apparatus. All formulations, all terms and concepts must be carefully verified, do not contain conventions and ambiguities. It is important that the parties put the same meaning into them.

The substantive part of the contract does not have any specific scheme and is based on the subject of the contract. An absolute requirement for the text of the contract in this part should be logical consistency, completeness of coverage of problematic provisions, clarity of wording and thoughtfulness of structural construction. An international treaty, regardless of the number of its participants and the subject of regulation is always norm-forming in the sense that it contains legal norms based on the coordination of the will and interests of states. Another thing is that these may be norms universal or local, authorizing or binding, imperative or dispositive, but in one way or another every international treaty is a source of international law. The text of the agreement should be carefully translated into the languages of the

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participating countries. In addition, it is compiled in English as the generally recognized language of international communication.

When designing and during the preparation of the text of the contract, certain universal requirements and techniques of legal technique developed by practice are used. They concern language, structure, design, etc. As an example, Methodological recommendations for the development of draft international treaties concluded within the framework of the CIS can be cited.

The section, which is called "Legal technique", contains the necessary list of general requirements for an international treaty: completeness of legal regulation of the relevant sphere of relations; absence of contradictions both in the treaty itself and with other norms of international law; clarity, simplicity and accessibility of the language of the treaty; the logical sequence of the presentation of the content of the contract; brevity; elimination of duplication; concreteness and accuracy of formulations, uniformity of use of concepts and terms.

A special section is devoted to the linguistic and terminological requirements for the project. It is presented in Russian. The terms and concepts used must be identical in meaning and content. Each concept is denoted by a corresponding term, and the same terms are used to denote the same concepts. It is advisable to

give definitions of little-known special terms. If the terms are ambiguous, the project specifies what meaning is attached to them. The terminology of the project should correspond to the generally accepted in international practice and, if possible, in the national legislation of the participating States. The wording should be clear, abbreviations are only generally accepted.

Definitions of terms relevant to the draft treaty as a whole are given in its separate structural part, usually placed at the beginning of the main (substantive) part of the text. Definitions of terms relevant to the part of the draft agreement are given in this part of the draft. It is customary to formulate the provisions of an international treaty in singular constructions. For example: "... competent authority of each of the Parties ...", and not "... competent authorities of the Parties ...", etc.

Much attention is paid to the correct use of the names of official bodies and organizations. They are given in exact accordance with the full official names provided for in the constituent documents and other acts.

With repeated use of a particular name (concept) in the text of the draft agreement at the first use, the full official name is given, and then the generally accepted abbreviated version. For example: "Member States of the Commonwealth of Independent States (hereinafter referred to as the CIS member States)".

In order to avoid repetitions in the text of the contract, various kinds of references are used. These may be references to certain provisions of the treaty itself, as well as to other existing international legal acts. In the latter case, it is necessary to indicate the official name of the document, the date of its adoption, as well as the exact indication of the provision to which reference is made. In case of repeated use of the name, the previously agreed abbreviated model is also used. When mentioned in the text of the contract (project treaties) fundamental international documents, for example, the Charter of the United Nations, the Charter of the Commonwealth of Independent States, etc., their details should not be given.

If a reference is made in the contract (draft contract) to the provisions contained therein, then this is necessarily stipulated using the adjective "present". It is not recommended to refer to the reference norm and other norms if there are difficulties in understanding the meaning of the normative regulation. Stages of acceptance of the treaty: agreement of the text, acceptance of the text, authentication of the text, signing of the treaty, ratification, approval, accession, reservation.

Ratification is the approval of a contract by the highest state authority, after which it becomes mandatory for the state.

A reservation - is a unilateral official statement by a State when signing, ratifying, accepting or approving an international treaty or acceding to it, through which the State wishes to exclude or modify the legal effect of certain provisions of the treaty in their application to that State. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that a reservation is not always possible. A treaty may contain a prohibition on certain types of reservations, or the reservation is incompatible with the object and purpose of the treaty. There is a certain order of registration reservations. A State party to the treaty may withdraw a reservation or objection to it at any time at its discretion.

The Protocol as a type of international treaty is most often used to specify a certain range of issues on which an agreement is being implemented. Even being part of another agreement, the protocol may be of a closed, secret characteristic.

Memorandum (from Lat. memorandum – what should be remembered) is a diplomatic document that, with a certain degree of conditionality, can be considered as a treaty, since it contains an agreement on the understanding of a provision or on the intentions to follow it. In the memoranda, the States demonstrate their agreed intentions.

It is quite rare both in educational and scientific literature that the charter is mentioned as an international treaty. The point, apparently, is that the charter is a

common name for a large number of heterogeneous documents. In the Middle Ages and in Modern times, documents of a public legal nature were so called. For example, English The Magna Carta of 1215, the People's Charter – the political program of the Chartists in England, the Charter of the French Language – the law establishing the status of the French language in Quebec, and in international law, this term has been used relatively recently for international legal acts of a recommendatory nature, similar in meaning and significance to international declarations adopted at the interstate level by States – subjects of international law.

The parties agree on the form of acceptance of the agreement during negotiations, and if the agreement is adopted within the framework of an international conference, its adoption is governed by the rules of procedure. The text of the bilateral agreements is adopted unanimously. Multilateral treaties can be adopted by consensus (if this is determined in advance, for example, voting on the final Act of the Helsinki Meeting in 1975) or by voting (as a general rule, two-thirds of the votes of the participants are required). The establishment of authenticity means the final recognition of the text by the parties. Most often this is done by initialing (affixing initials of authorized persons). Other procedures are also possible. Often, the authenticity stage coincides with the signing of the contract and the adoption of a resolution opening the contract for signature.

The signing of the contract means the acceptance by the State of the obligations arising from the contract. These obligations come within the time period established by the contract immediately, if the contract is not subsequent ratification. The obligation of ratification is determined by Article 14 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties.

As already noted above, in addition to the actual contract (agreement), there are varieties that have their own legal and technical features. A special type of contract is a convention (from the Latin *conventio* – contract, agreement). It does not contain any significant differences from the "classical" understanding of the contract. Moreover, a convention is, as a rule, a larger multilateral treaty on some significant issue. The Convention is distinguished by the breadth of coverage of the subject of regulation, which to some extent makes it related to the code.

Often enough conventions are adopted under the auspices of international organizations (UN, its special agencies – UNESCO, ILO, ICAO, an example is the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, signed by November 4, 1950 in Rome by the member countries of the Council of Europe. Working on conventions requires a lot of effort and time, and often stretches for many years.

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